

METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF GLICLAZIDE, METFORMIN HYDROCHLORIDE AND PIOGLITAZONE HYDROCHLORIDE IN BULK AND TABLET DOSAGE FORM BY RP- UPLC

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Abstract:

A simple, accurate, precise method was developed and validated of Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride in bulk and tablet dosage form. Chromatogram was run through shimadzu LC-2010CHT C18 column (5×2.1mm,1.9 micron). Mobile phase containing Acetic acid: Methanol: Acetonitrile(30:20:50%w/v/v) was pumped through column at a flow rate of 0.3ml/min. Ambient temperature was maintained. 270nm wavelength were used for Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride. Retention time of Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride were found to be 3.38 min, 1.78 min and 2.49 min. %RSD of system precision for Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride were found to be 0.0655, 0.0342, 0.0565 respectively. %RSD of method precision for Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride were found to be 0.3851, 0.3766, 0.5668 respectively. % Recovery was obtained as 100.60, 98.73, 100.38 for Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride. LOD values was obtained from regression equations for Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride were found to be 0.0423, 0.3064, 0.0076 respectively. LOQ values was obtained from regression equations for Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride were found to be 0.1283, 0.9286, 0.0232 respectively. Regression equation of Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride were found to be $y = 1465.6x + 263.00893$, $y = 26724x + 7832$ and $y = 4487.6x + 1691.517$ respectively. Retention times are decreased, so the method developed was simple and economical that can be adopted in regular quality control test in pharmaceutical industries.

Key words: Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride.

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INTRODUCTION:**Gliclazide:**

Gliclazide is an oral antihyperglycemic agent used for the treatment of non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM). It belongs to the sulfonyl urea class of insulin secretagogues, which act by stimulating β cells of the pancreas to release insulin. Sulfonyl ureas increase both basal insulin secretion and meal-stimulated insulin release. Medications in this class differ in the absorption, duration of action, route of elimination and binding site on their target pancreatic β cell receptor. Sulfonyl ureas also increase peripheral glucose utilization, decrease hepatic gluconeogenesis and may increase the number and sensitivity of insulin receptors. Sulfonyl ureas are associated with weight gain, through less so than insulin. Due to their mechanism of action, sulfonyl ureas may cause hypoglycemia and require consistent food intake to decrease this risk. The risk of hypoglycemia is increased in elderly, debilitated and malnourished individuals. Gliclazide has been shown to decrease fasting plasma glucose, postprandil blood glucose and glycosolated haemoglobin (HbA1c) levels (reflective of the last 8-10 weeks of glucose control). Gliclazide is extensively metabolized by the liver, its metabolites are excreted in both urine (60-70%) and faeces (10-20%).

Structure for gliclazide:**Figure- 1 Gliclazide Metformin hydrochloride:**

Metformin hydrochloride (MET) is 1,1- dimethyl biguanide hydrochloride, a biguanide antidiabetic. It is given orally in the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus and is the drug of choice in overweight patients. They do not stimulate insulin release but require that some insulin be present in order to exert their antidiabetic effect. Possible mechanism of action includes the delay in the absorption of glucose from the GIT and increase in insulin sensitivity and glucose uptake in to cells and inhibition of hepatic gluconeogenesis. For effective control of blood sugar in diabetic patients more than one medication is required. It reduces blood glucose levels, by improving hepatic and peripheral tissue sensitivity to insulin without affecting the secretion of insulin. There is substantial inter- individual variability in response to MET, leading to research on MET pharmacokinetics to predict variations in response

as well as aid the tailoring of MET therapy.

Structure for metformin hydrochloride:**Figure- 2 Metformin hydrochloride****Pioglitazone hydrochloride:**

Pioglitazone hydrochloride[(± pyridine) ethoxy] phenyl] methyl]-2,4-] thiazolidinedione mono hydrochloride. It is an oral anti-diabetic agent belonging to the class of thiazolidinediones that acts primarily by decreasing insulin resistance. It is a peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor γ (PPAR γ) agonist that increases transcription of insulin- responsive genes and thus increases insulin sensitivity. It is used in the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus. It improves sensitivity to insulin in muscle and adipose tissue and inhibits hepatic gluconeogenesis also improves glycemic control while reducing circulating insulin levels.

Structure for pioglitazone hydrochloride:**Figure- 3 Pioglitazone hydrochloride****MATERIALS AND REAGENTS**

New triclazone-40 (sun pharma laboratories ltd), containing 40 mg of Gliclazide, 500 mg of Metformin hydrochloride and 15 mg of Pioglitazone hydrochloride was procured from local pharmacy. Methanol (AR grade), Methanol (HPLC grade), Acetonitrile (HPLC grade), Water (HPLC grade), Acetic acid and Triethylamine were purchased from Qualigens India Pvt Limited, Mumbai and Loba cheme India limited, Mumbai.

INSTRUMENTATION AND CHROMATOGRAPHIC CONDITIONS

Different Instrument used to carry out the present work are, Shimadzu AUX- 220 Digital balance, Shimadzu LC-2010CHT. The following optimized conditions were employed for analysis of Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride by Isocratic RP-UPLC method, Mode of operation – Isocratic, Stationary phase - C18 column (5×2.1mm, 1.9 micron),

Mobile phase - Acetic acid: Methanol: Acetonitrile with adjusted pH 5.5 using Triethylamine Ratio - 30:20:50 % v/v/v, Detection wavelength - 270nm, Flow rate - 0.3ml/min, Temperature – Ambient, Sample load - 2 μ L.

SAMPLE PROCESSING

Stability of Sample Solutions

Solutions of Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride (10 μ g/mL) were checked for their stability of absorbance at 270nm and it was found that three drugs are stable for approximately 3 hours.

Preparation of standard stock solution

The standard stock solutions were prepared with methanol to give the final concentration of 1000 μ g/ml. The working standard solutions of Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride were prepared by taking suitable aliquots of drug solution from the standard solutions and the volume was made up to 10 ml with methanol to get concentrations of 4-20 μ g/ml of Gliclazide, 25-500 μ g/ml of Metformin hydrochloride and 1-7.5 μ g/ml of Pioglitazone hydrochloride.

Preparation of calibration graph

From the mixed standard stock solution, aliquots are made with diluents to get the concentration of 25-500 μ g/ml of Metformin hydrochloride, 1-7.5 μ g/ml of Pioglitazone hydrochloride and 4-20 μ g/ml of Gliclazide. The solution of 20 μ L was injected into the column. All measurements were repeated six times for each concentration. The peak areas were plotted against concentration and the calibration curve was constructed.

Quantification of formulation

Twenty tablets of formulation (NEW TRICLAZONE-40) containing 40 mg of Gliclazide, 500 mg of Metformin hydrochloride and 15 mg of Pioglitazone hydrochloride were accurately weighed and powdered. The powder was equivalent to 40 mg of Gliclazide, 500 mg of Metformin hydrochloride and 15 mg of Pioglitazone hydrochloride was weighed respectively and transferred to a standard volumetric flask and dissolved in methanol. The mixture was sonicated

for 15 minutes to dissolve drugs and then volume was made up to the mark with methanol. The solution was finally filtered to collect the filtrate containing extracted Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride which was diluted appropriately with methanol to obtain the final concentration of 40 μ g/ml of Gliclazide, 500 μ g/ml of Metformin hydrochloride and 15 μ g/ml of Pioglitazone hydrochloride. A steady baseline was recorded with optimized chromatographic conditions. After the stabilization of baseline for one hour, six test solutions of formulation were injected and recorded the chromatograms. The concentration of each test solution was determined by using slope and intercept values from the calibration graph.

Validation of Developed Method Linearity

The Linearity of the method was studied by injecting the mixed standard solutions in the concentration range of 4-20 μ g/mL of Gliclazide, 25-500 μ g/mL of Metformin hydrochloride and 1-7.5 μ g/mL of Pioglitazone hydrochloride injected six times into the UPLC system keeping the injection volume constant. The peak areas were plotted against the corresponding concentrations to obtain the calibration graphs.

Precision

The repeatability of the method was checked by repeated analysis of the formulation for six times with same concentration. The amount of each drug present in the formulation was calculated. The percentage RSD value was calculated.

Accuracy

Accuracy of the method was confirmed by recovery studies. To the pre-analysed formulation a known quantity of the standard drug solution was added and the amount of each drug recovered was calculated. The percentage RSD value was calculated.

LOD and LOQ

The linearity study were carried out for three times. The LOD and LOQ were calculated based up on the calibration curve method. The LOD and LOQ were calculated by using the average of slope and standard deviation of response.

TABLE-1 SYSTEM SUITABILITY PARAMETERS FOR THE OPTIMIZED CHROMATOGRAM BY RP-UPLC

PARAMETERS	GLICLAZIDE	METFORMIN HYDROCHLORIDE	PIOGLITAZONE HYDROCHLORIDE
Retention time	3.38	1.78	2.49
Tailing factor	1.24	1.35	1.30
Theoretical plates	3135	2752	2425
Resolution	2.129	0.000	2.032

Figure-4 System Suitability Chromatogram

<Chromatogram>

PeakTable

Name	Ret. Time	Area	Area %	Tailing Factor	Resolution
Metformin Hcl	1.78	2669546	81.74	1.35	0.000
Pioglitazone Hcl	2.49	449945	13.78	1.29	2.030
Gliclazide	3.39	146230	4.48	1.24	2.124
		3265721	100.00		

Specificity

Figure-5 Blank chromatogram

<Chromatogram>

PeakTable

Detector A Ch1 270nm

Figure-7 Calibration curve for Metformin hydrochloride

Figure- 8 Calibration curve for Pioglitazone

Table-2 Recovery Analysis of Formulation (New triclozone-40) by RP-UPLC

Drug	Percentage	Amount present ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount added (%)	Percentage recovered	Average % recovery	S.D	%RSD	S.E
GLI	100	40.00	110%	100.16	100.60	0.3950	0.3926	0.2280
	100	40.00	120%	100.75				
	100	40.00	130%	100.91				
MET	100	100.00	110%	99.57	98.73	0.1457	0.1491	0.0841
	100	100.00	120%	99.80				
	100	100.00	130%	99.84				
PIO	100	15.00	110%	99.65	100.38	0.7968	0.7937	0.4600
	100	15.00	120%	100.26				
	100	15.00	130%	100.38				

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

A 10 μ g/mL solution of both Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride were prepared in the diluent methanol. The solutions were scanned between 200 to 400 nm and the spectra were recorded. Both Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride have marked absorbance at 270 nm and hence it was selected as the detection wavelength. The drug Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride was found to be stable for 3 hours respectively. Initial separations were done using combinations of Acetic acid, Methanol and Acetonitrile in different ratios. The mobile phase consisting of Acetic acid: Methanol: Acetonitrile with adjusted pH 5.5 by using Triethylamine in the ratio of 30:20:50%v/v/v was selected after calculating all system suitability test parameters, and the same was used at a flow rate 0.3ml/min and optimized chromatogram. The stock solution of Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride were prepared in the diluent (Acetic acid: Methanol: Acetonitrile 30:20:50%v/v/v) and mixture of the three drugs in the concentration range of 4–20 μ g/ml of Gliclazide, 25–500 μ g/ml of Metformin hydrochloride and 1–7.5 μ g/ml of Pioglitazone hydrochloride were prepared from the stock solution using diluent. The solutions were injected into the column and the chromatograms were recorded. The calibration curve was plotted with peak area versus concentration and the correlation coefficient was found to be 0.9999, 0.9998 and 0.9997 for Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride respectively. The optical characters like correlation coefficient, slope, intercept, LOD and LOQ were calculated. From the tablet dosage form New tricalzone-40 (40mg of Gliclazide, 500mg of Metformin hydrochloride and 15 mg of Pioglitazone hydrochloride), a solution containing 40 μ g/ml of Gliclazide, 500 μ g/ml of Metformin hydrochloride was prepared and it contains 15 μ g/ml of Pioglitazone hydrochloride theoretically. The solution was injected and chromatogram was recorded. The procedure was repeated six times to confirm precision of the method. The percentage purity of the drugs was found to be 99.93 \pm 0.38485 of Gliclazide, 99.95 \pm 0.37665 of Metformin hydrochloride and 99.81 \pm 0.56683 of Pioglitazone hydrochloride. The %RSD was found to be 0.38512 of Gliclazide, 0.37684 of Metformin hydrochloride and 0.5679 of Pioglitazone hydrochloride. Further the precision of the method was confirmed by intraday and interday analysis. Interday and intraday analysis of formulation was done on three times on same day and one time on three consecutive days. The percentage RSD for the intraday and interday

precision was found to be 0.0708 and 0.0655, 0.1898 and 0.3429, 0.08615 and 0.5657 for Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride respectively. The low percentage RSD values indicated that the precision of the method was confirmed. The confidence interval 95% of intraday analysis was found to be in the range of 99.95 and 100.09 for Gliclazide, 100.60 and 100.98 for Metformin hydrochloride and 99.99 and 100.16 for Pioglitazone hydrochloride respectively. The confidence interval 95% of interday analysis was found to be in the range of 99.90 and 100.03 for Gliclazide, 100.45 and 101.10 for Metformin hydrochloride and 99.79 and 100.80 for Pioglitazone hydrochloride, respectively. The accuracy of the method was confirmed by the recovery study. To the pre-analysed samples, a known quantity of the drug was added at three 110%, 120%, 130% different concentrations and the chromatogram was recorded. The % recovery of Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride are 100.16 to 100.91, 99.57 to 99.84 and 99.65 to 101.23 respectively. The % RSD for Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride are 0.3926, 0.1491 and 0.7937 respectively. The low % RSD and high % RSD recovery values suggest that there is no interference from the excipients during the analysis of the formulation.

CONCLUSION:

The new Ultra High Performance Chromatography method were developed for Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride and Pioglitazone hydrochloride in bulk and tablet dosage form.

These developed method were continuous and interrelated process that measures a parameter was intended and establishes the performance limit of the measurements.

The selection of solvent, column, buffer, detector, wavelength and other conditions play a dramatic role in the method development and validation of Gliclazide, Metformin hydrochloride, Pioglitazone hydrochloride in tablet dosage form.

These developed method were validated according to ICH Guidelines with various parameters like precision, Accuracy, LOD and LOQ etc.

The advantage of these method was high Selectivity, Sensitivity, Economic, Precise and Accurate method.

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